

Dimorphosim of a dimethoxy bridged oxovanadium(v)-hydrazone complex

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Abstract : A monoclinic variety with $C2/c$ space group of the title complex $[V^VO(L)(OCH_3)]_2$, incorporating the doubly deprotonated benzoyl hydrazone of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone (H_2L) was synthesized from the decomposition of $[V^{IV}O(L)(bipy)]$ (where $bipy$ representing the 2,2'-bipyridine) in methanol which has been reported very recently from our laboratory. In this paper we report another monoclinic variety of this complex with $P2_1/n$ space group that showed some differences in bonding patterns in the solid state (but in solution they are almost identical) prepared by different synthetic method viz. from the equimolar reaction of $[V^{IV}O(acac)_2]$, H_2L and imidazole in CH_3OH .

Keywords : Oxovanadium(V) complex, hydrazone complex, crystal structure, dimorphism.

Introduction

As a part of our program on the synthesis and characterization of new oxovanadium(IV/V) complexes with a family of benzoyl hydrazones of 2-hydroxyacetophenone and its 5-substituted derivatives¹⁻⁷, we have seen that these hydrazone ligands are very suitable in stabilizing the vanadium in its highest oxidation (+V) state and the nature of the product depends upon the reaction medium. $[V^VO_3(L)_2]$ type of complexes⁵ are formed if the equimolar amount of $[V^{IV}O(acac)_2]$ and H_2L are allowed to react in a non-hydroxylic solvent like acetone, CH_2Cl_2 , acetonitrile etc., while the similar reaction mixture yielded the $[V^VO(L)(OCH_3)]$ complex if the non-hydroxylic solvent is replaced by methanol⁷. The monoclinic crystal-

line variety of $[V^VO(L)(OCH_3)]_2$ complex with $C2/c$ space group was obtained from the decomposition of $[V^{IV}O(L)(bipy)]$ complex in methanol⁷. Though the polymorphism is not an unusual phenomenon^{5,6} in the metal-ligand complexes but till date no such example is available for the methoxy bonded oxovanadium(V)-hydrazone complexes. Herein, we report the synthesis and structural characterization of a different crystalline variety of $[V^VO(L)(OCH_3)]_2$ complex [where L^{2-} represents the doubly deprotonated benzoyl hydrazone of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone (H_2L , I)], which is believed to be the first report of dimorphism in this area. Such studies are important in connection with the catalytic⁸⁻¹² and medicinal¹³⁻¹⁶ activities of vanadium complexes.

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Results and discussion

The monoclinic crystals of the complex $[V^VO(L)(OCH_3)_2]$ (with $P2_1/n$ space group) were obtained from the equimolar reaction of $[V^{IV}O(acac)_2]$, H_2L and imidazole in methanol which can be represented as :

In this monoclinic variety of the complex, crystals belong to the $P2_1/n$ space group compared to the $C2/c$ space group observed in its other variety⁷. The dimeric structure of this variety is illustrated in Fig. 1 and the molecu-

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of $[VO(L)(OCH_3)_2]$ complex showing the atom numbering scheme with ellipsoid at 50% probability.

lar dimensions are collected in Table 1. Like its other variety⁷ this dimer also lies on a crystallographic center of symmetry formed by two bridging methoxide-O atoms with V-O(4) and V-O(4)\$ [symmetry code \$ = -x, -y, -z] having bond lengths of 2.3733(12) and 1.8279(13) Å respectively. The V...V separation is 3.357(1) Å and the angle V-O(4)-V(\$\$) is 105.33(6)° which is very similar with its other variety⁷. The coordination sphere of the metal is of the VO_5N type and the geometry at the metal center is distorted octahedral with oxo oxygen O(1) and a methoxide-O at the apex. The phenolate O(2), the enolate O(3), the imine nitrogen N(1) atoms of the fully deprotonated (L)²⁻ ligand in its enol form and a symmetry

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (°) of the complex

Bond distances :			
V-O(1)	1.5864(13)	V-O(4)(\$\$)	1.8279(13)
V-O(2)	1.8265(13)	V-N(1)	2.1073(16)
V-O(3)	1.9381(12)	V-V(\$\$)	3.357(1)
V-O(4)	2.3733(12)		
Bond angles :			
O(1)-V-O(2)	101.09(7)	O(3)-V-O(4)	78.94(5)
O(1)-V-O(3)	99.82(6)	O(3)-V-N(1)	74.72(6)
O(1)-V-O(4)	177.82(6)	O(4)(\$\$)-V-O(3)	89.62(6)
O(1)-V-N(1)	98.28(7)	O(4)-V-O(4)(\$\$)	74.67(6)
O(1)-V-O(4)(\$\$)	103.60(6)	O(4)(\$\$)-V(1)-N(1)	155.00(6)
O(2)-V-O(3)	151.14(6)	V-O(4)-V(\$\$)	105.33(6)
O(2)-V-N(1)	82.75(6)	N(1)-V-O(4)	115.8(2)
O(2)-V-O(4)	80.71(5)	N(2)-N(1)-V	115.20(11)
O(2)-V-O(4)(\$\$)	104.46(6)		

\$ = -x, -y, -z

related bridging methoxide-O(4)\$ atom of the neighbouring molecule constitute the tetragonal plane (with an r.m.s. deviation of 0.01 Å) from which the V atom is displaced by 0.362(1) Å towards the terminal O(1) atom. The coordinated hydrazone ligand generates a folded six-membered and an almost planar (with an r.m.s. deviation of 0.073 Å) five-membered chelate ring at the metal center. The corresponding bite angles are 82.75(6)° and 74.72(6)°, which are very similar with its dimorph and also other reported hydrazone complexes^{7,17-19}. The C-O, C-N and N-N distances of the five-membered chelate ring are consistent with the enolate form of the amide. The atoms of the ligand are also symmetrically disposed relative to the center of the $[VO(\mu_2-OCH_3)_2VO]^{4+}$ core and the disposition of the oxovanadium groups is anti-coplanar which is also observed in other methoxy-bridged oxovanadium(V) complexes^{7,17-19}. The V-O bond lengths are relatively shorter than its dimorph⁷ and follow the general order : V-O(oxo) < V-O(phenoxide) < V-O(methoxide)_e (e = equatorial) < V-O(enolate) < V-O(methoxide)_a (a = axial).

The main differences between the present crystalline variety and the recently reported other variety of this complex are : (i) it belongs to the $P2_1/n$ space group compared to the $C2/c$ space group observed in its other

variety⁷ and (ii) in the structure (Fig. 1) of this variety, the symmetry related methoxide-O(4) atom occupies one of the four equatorial positions (which is not usual) compared to its usual axial position *trans* to vanadyl oxygen

plex. The solid-state structural features of this dimorph (which otherwise display identical chemical composition and solution properties) differ in the space group and in bonding pattern.

Scheme 1

observed in its other variety⁷ and also such type of other complexes¹⁷⁻¹⁹. This unusual behaviour can be explained by considering the relatively higher basicity of imidazole molecule²⁰ ($\text{pK}_a = 7.33$) in comparison to the solvent methanol. Being the higher basic, initially imidazole occupies one of the four equatorial positions of the V^{IV} [as $\text{V}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{acac})_2$ being the starting material] along with the meridionally disposed deprotonated hydrazone ligand and a solvent methanol molecule occupies the axial position *trans* to vanadyl oxygen. Under this ligand environment, the V^{IV} is unstable and it undergoes spontaneous aerial oxidation to V^{V} . V^{V} being the hard acid, it prefers relatively harder methoxide oxygen atom than the relatively soft imidazole nitrogen atom. So, the V-N(imidazole) bond is broken and this position is occupied by one coordinated methoxide group of the neighbouring molecule. Synthetic paths for the formation of these two crystalline varieties have been represented in Scheme 1.

Conclusion :

The virtually unknown dimorph of methoxy-bridged dimeric oxovanadium(V)-hydrazone complex containing VO^{3+} motif has been realized in the present com-

Experimental

Materials :

2-Hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone was procured from Aldrich. Benzoyl hydrazine was purchased from E. Merck. Acetylacetone, vanadyl sulphate pentahydrate and imidazole were obtained from Loba Chemical Company (India). H_2L ligand¹ and $[\text{V}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{acac})_2]$ ²¹ were synthesized by the reported methods. All other reagents were of A. R. grade, obtained from commercial sources and used without further purification.

Preparation of the metal complexes :

The complex was synthesized in the following way : To a methanol solution (20 cm^3) of H_2L (0.27 g, 1.0 mmol) and imidazole (0.07 g, 1 mmol), methanol solution (20 cm^3) of $[\text{V}^{\text{IV}}\text{O}(\text{acac})_2]$ (0.265 g, 1.0 mmol) was added. This mixture was heated under reflux for 1 h and kept for slow evaporation at room temperature. After 4 days black crystals of $[\text{V}^{\text{VO}}\text{O}(\text{L})(\text{OCH}_3)_2]$ were obtained in 88% yield. The analytical, spectral (IR, UV/Vis and ^1H NMR) and electrochemical data are identical (within experimental error) with its other crystalline variety reported earlier⁷.

X-Ray data collection and refinement :

For X-ray structure determination, data were measured with Mo K α radiation at 150 K using the Oxford Diffraction X-calibur CCD system. Data analyses were carried out with the CrysAlis program²² and the structure was solved using direct methods with the SHELXS-97 program²³. Absorption corrections were carried out with the ABSPACK program²⁴ and the non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters. The hydrogen atoms bonded to carbon were included in geometric positions and given thermal parameters equivalent to 1.2 times those of the atom to which they were attached. The structures were refined on F^2 using SHELXL-97 program²³ and the molecular graphics were computed using PLATON²⁵. All crystallographic data are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Crystal data and structure determination summary of the complex

Empirical formula	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ V
Formula weight	364.27
Crystal colour	black
Crystal system	monoclinic
Space group	$P2_1/n$
a (Å)	9.9415(3)
b (Å)	15.4723(7)
c (Å)	10.5534(4)
α (°)	90
β (°)	94.189(3)
γ (°)	90
V (Å ³)	1618.96(11)
Z	4
ρ_{calc} (g cm ⁻³)	1.494
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.636
$F(000)$	752
Data/restraints/parameters	4671/0/220
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	0.747
R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I_0)$] $R1$, $wR2$	0.0369, 0.0876
R indices (all data) $R1$, $wR2$	0.0693, 0.0975

Supplementary material :

CCDC 714726 contains the supplementary crystallographic data which can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : (+44) 1223-336-033; or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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